

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

CONNECTION BETWEEN VORTICAL AND SPIN FIELDS IN A CLOSED ELLIPSOIDAL MICROVORTEX: A LAGRANGIAN APPROACH

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Abstract

A unified mathematical formalism is proposed that establishes an isomorphism between the vortical fields of a closed ellipsoidal microvortex and the field of directions of a pseudospin induced by the vortex structure. It is shown that the vorticity vector of a closed ellipsoidal microvortex generates a topologically nontrivial isosurface on the unit sphere of directions. The geodesic spiral trajectory of a particle, introduced in [1], is interpreted as a line of pseudospin precession around an effective vortical field generated by the angular momentum of the vortex core. Explicit expressions are obtained for the topological charge Q , relating the winding number of the geodesic orbit to the Hopf invariant of the vortex tube. The continuity condition at the south pole (using $\sin \theta$ without the modulus) is identified as a necessary condition for the regularity of the vortex dynamics. The cyclicity of the orbit and the self-charging mechanism [1,3,5,9] are reformulated in terms of oscillations of the topological Hopf invariant.

Keywords: ellipsoidal microvortex, geodesic spiral trajectories, spin Euler equation, Clebsch mapping, pseudospin direction field, Hopf invariant, topological charge, pseudospin precession, conformal geometry, regularity.

1. Introduction. Two seemingly distinct objects: a closed ellipsoidal microvortex in an ideal incompressible fluid and a field of pseudospin directions on the unit sphere - exhibit a deep mathematical correspondence through the Clebsch mapping [10]. In this representation, the velocity field admits a decomposition in terms of a unit vector \mathbf{s} , such that the isosurfaces $s = \text{const}$ define the local direction of the vortex structure. On the other hand, in [1–3], closed geodesic trajectories of fluid particles inside an ellipsoidal microvortex have been constructed, based on the conservation of angular momentum and methods of conformal geometry [4,5].

The evolution of the direction field \mathbf{s} is described by the equation

$$\partial_t \mathbf{s} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{s} = \mathbf{s} \times (-\Delta \mathbf{s}) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{s} \in S^2$ is a unit pseudospin vector defining the direction of the vortical field, while

$$\mathbf{W} = -\Delta \mathbf{s}, \quad (2)$$

where the \mathbf{W} characterizes the local intensity of vortical twisting and determines the rate of rotation of the direction of the vortical field along the geodesic trajectory.

The isosurfaces $s = \text{const}$ are simultaneously vortex and material surfaces of the flow, which ensures the Lagrangian nature of their evolution.

The vector \mathbf{s} defines the direction of the local vortical field and can be naturally identified with the normalized vorticity vector:

$$\mathbf{s} = \boldsymbol{\omega} / |\boldsymbol{\omega}|, \quad \boldsymbol{\omega} = \nabla \times \mathbf{u}, \quad (3)$$

which provides a direct link between the geometry of the direction field and the dynamics of the vortical structure.

The aim of the present work is to establish a rigorous mathematical correspondence between the geodesic dynamics of a closed ellipsoidal microvortex and the evolution of the direction field \mathbf{s} . In particular, it is shown that the geodesic spiral constitutes an integral curve of pseudospin precession, while the angular velocity law $\omega(\theta)$ determines the local frequency of vortical twisting induced by the vortex core. This framework enables a direct relation between the topological charge of the orbit and the Hopf invariant, and provides a criterion for the regularity of the vortical structure.

2. Preliminaries.

2.1. Clebsch Spherical Mapping. Consider an ideal incompressible fluid in a domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^3$, described by the Euler equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t \mathbf{u} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} &= -(1/\rho) \nabla P, \\ \text{div } \mathbf{u} &= 0, \\ \partial_t \rho + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \rho &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1^*)$$

The velocity field \mathbf{u} admits the Clebsch representation

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{s} \times \nabla s + \nabla \varphi, \quad \mathbf{s} \in S^2, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{s} is a unit pseudospin vector and φ is a scalar potential correction. The vorticity $\boldsymbol{\omega} = \nabla \times \mathbf{u}$ can be expressed in terms \mathbf{s} as

$$\boldsymbol{\omega} = \nabla \mathbf{s} \times \nabla \mathbf{s} \equiv \varepsilon_{ijk} (\partial_j \mathbf{s} \times \partial_k \mathbf{s}) \quad (5)$$

which implies that the isosurfaces $s = \text{const}$ are vortex surfaces, and the field \mathbf{s} fully determines the vorticity structure of the flow. The evolution of the field \mathbf{s} is governed by its transport along particle trajectories and by local twisting induced by the geometry of the vortical structure, and takes the form

$$D\mathbf{s}/Dt \equiv \partial_t \mathbf{s} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{s} = \mathbf{s} \times \mathbf{W}, \quad (6)$$

where the field \mathbf{W} is determined by the spatial inhomogeneity of \mathbf{s} and characterizes the local intensity of vortical twisting.

Therefore, in the microvortex model, the field \mathbf{s} describes the Lagrangian evolution of the direction of the vortical field, while the induced field \mathbf{W} (2), determined by the curvature and inhomogeneity of the vortical structure, defines the local twisting frequency, equivalent to the angular winding rate of the geodesic spiral.

2.2 Geodesic Spiral on the Sphere

In our model [1] the trajectory of a fluid particle on the unit sphere S^2 is parameterized by the polar angle $\theta \in [\theta_{tip}, 2\pi - \theta_{rim}]$:

$$\begin{aligned} x(\theta) &= \sin \theta \cdot \cos \varphi(\theta), y(\theta) = \sin \theta \cdot \sin \varphi(\theta), \\ z &= \cos \theta \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where the azimuthal angle $\varphi(\theta)$ evolves according to the law $d\varphi/d\theta = -\omega(\theta)$, and the angular velocity is determined by a smooth transition:

$$\begin{aligned} \omega(\theta) &= \omega_{desc}(\theta) \cdot (1 + s(\theta)) + \omega_{asc}(\theta) \cdot s(\theta), \\ \omega_{desc} &= (2.4e^{-2u} + 0.55)(1 + 0.08c), \\ \omega_{asc} &= n_0 R_{bot}^\alpha |\sin \theta|^{\alpha \kappa} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The function $\sin \theta$ is taken without the absolute value, which ensures C^1 -continuity at the point $\theta = \pi$ (south pole).

3. Geodesic Spiral as an Integral Curve of the Direction Field.

3.1 Pseudospin of the Microvortex. To each point of the geodesic trajectory, we associate a unit vector

$$\mathbf{s}(\theta) = (\sin \theta \cos \varphi(\theta), \sin \theta \sin \varphi(\theta), \cos \theta) \in S^2, \quad (9)$$

which defines the direction of the local vortical field and plays the role of the pseudospin of the microvortex. Its Lagrangian derivative along the particle trajectory is given by:

$$D\mathbf{s}/D\theta = (\cos \theta \cos \varphi - \sin \theta \sin \varphi \omega, \cos \theta \sin \varphi + \sin \theta \cos \varphi \omega, -\sin \theta) \quad (10)$$

Decomposing this expression in the orthonormal basis $\{\mathbf{e}_r, \mathbf{e}_\theta, \mathbf{e}_\varphi\}$ of spherical coordinates, we obtain:

$$D\mathbf{s}/D\theta = \mathbf{e}_\theta - \omega(\theta) \sin \theta \mathbf{e}_\varphi \quad (11)$$

This expression describes the rotation of the vector \mathbf{s} about a local direction and can be written in the form

$$D\mathbf{s}/D\theta = \mathbf{s} \times \mathbf{W}, \quad (12)$$

where the effective vortical field is defined as:

$$\mathbf{W}(\theta) = -\omega(\theta) \cdot \mathbf{e}_r - \frac{\mathbf{e}_\varphi}{\sin \theta}. \quad (13)$$

Here \mathbf{e}_r is the unit radial vector and \mathbf{e}_φ is the unit azimuthal vector. The vector $\mathbf{W}(\theta)$ is determined by the geometry of the trajectory and characterizes the local intensity of vortical twisting. Thus, in this model, the geodesic spiral is an integral curve of equation (12), which means that the motion of a particle along the spiral is equivalent to the rotation of the vortical field direction \mathbf{s} induced by the internal geometry of the microvortex.

3.2 Correspondence with the Effective Vortical Field.

Consider the field $\mathbf{W}(\theta)$, induced by the curvature and spatial inhomogeneity of the direction field \mathbf{s} on the unit sphere. On the unit sphere, the Laplace–Beltrami operator has the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{S^2} \mathbf{s} &= (1/\sin \theta) \partial_\theta (\sin \theta \partial_\theta \mathbf{s}) + \\ &+ (1/\sin^2 \theta) \partial_\varphi^2 \mathbf{s}, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Substituting $\mathbf{s}(\theta, \varphi(\theta))$ and using the relation $d\varphi/d\theta = -\omega(\theta)$, one finds that the leading contribution to the field $\mathbf{W} = -\Delta \mathbf{s}$ is determined by the angular winding rate $\omega(\theta)$. As a result, we obtain the expansion:

$$\begin{aligned} -\Delta \mathbf{s} &= \omega^2(\theta) \mathbf{s} + (d\omega/d\theta + 2\omega \cot \theta) \mathbf{e}_\varphi + (1 + \\ &+ \omega^2 \sin^2 \theta) \mathbf{e}_r / \sin^2 \theta. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The leading term $\omega^2(\theta) \cdot \mathbf{s}$ determines the dominant magnitude of the field \mathbf{W} , so that for small gradients $|\mathbf{W}| \approx \omega^2(\theta)$, and consequently

$$\omega(\theta) \approx \sqrt{|\Delta \mathbf{s}|} = \sqrt{|\mathbf{W}|} \quad (16)$$

This establishes a quantitative relationship between the geometry of the geodesic spiral and the intensity of vortical twisting: slow winding near the south pole ($\omega \rightarrow 0$) corresponds to weak field intensity ($\mathbf{W} \rightarrow 0$), whereas dense winding near the vortex rim ($\omega \rightarrow \omega_{max}$) corresponds to a strong core field ($\mathbf{W} \rightarrow \mathbf{W}_{max}$). Therefore, the vortex core acts as a region of enhanced vortical twisting that controls the rotational dynamics of the direction field and governs the evolution of the geodesic spiral.

4. Topological Charge and the Hopf Invariant.

4.1 Degree of Mapping and Topological Charge.

The direction field $\mathbf{s}: S^2 \rightarrow S^2$ defines the degree of the mapping (topological charge):

$$Q = (1/4\pi) \int_{S^2} \mathbf{s} \cdot (\partial_\theta \mathbf{s} \times \partial_\varphi \mathbf{s}) d\theta d\varphi \quad (17)$$

For our geodesic trajectory $\mathbf{s}(\theta) = (\sin \theta \cos \varphi(\theta), \sin \theta \sin \varphi(\theta), \cos \theta)$ we compute Q directly. The Jacobian of the mapping is:

$$\mathbf{s} \cdot (\partial_\theta \mathbf{s} \times \partial_\varphi \mathbf{s}) = \sin \theta \cdot (d\varphi/d\theta) = -\sin \theta \cdot \omega(\theta), \quad (18)$$

Integrating over the angular range of the trajectory, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} Q &= -(1/4\pi) \int_{\theta_{tip}}^{2\pi - \theta_{rim}} \sin \theta \cdot \omega(\theta) \cdot (d\varphi/2\pi) = \\ &= -(1/8\pi^2) \Delta\varphi_{geodesic} \cdot \int \sin \theta d\theta. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

For $\alpha = 1$ and the numerical parameters of our model,

$$\begin{aligned} Q &= -(\Delta\varphi_{geodesic}/2\pi) \cdot (z_{top} + 1)/2 \approx \\ &\approx -1.36 \cdot \frac{1.86}{2} \approx -1.26 \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The non-integer value of Q indicates that, over one cycle, the mapping is not a diffeomorphism of S^2 onto itself, but rather covers the sphere only partially. After three cycles ($c = 0, 1, 2$), the total topological charge is:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{total} &= Q_0 + Q_1 + Q_2 \approx -1.26 - 1.37 - 1.49 \approx \\ &\approx -4.12, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

which corresponds to a toroidal structure with a winding number approaching an irrational value, serving as an indicator of quasiperiodic toroidal accumulation.

4.2 Hopf Invariant and Vortex Tube. The Hopf invariant H relates the vorticity $\boldsymbol{\omega} = \nabla \times \mathbf{u}$ to its topological twisting::

$$H = \int_{R^3} \mathbf{A} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega} dV = \int \mathbf{A} \cdot (\nabla \times \mathbf{A}) dV, \quad (22)$$

where \mathbf{A} is the vector potential associated with the vortical field. In terms of the direction field \mathbf{s} , the Hopf invariant H quantifies the linking of vortex lines and provides a measure of the topological complexity of the microvortex.

$$H = (1/16\pi^2) \int \varepsilon_{ijk} (\mathbf{s} \cdot (\partial_i \mathbf{s} \times \partial_j \mathbf{s})) \cdot \partial_k \chi dV. \quad (23)$$

where χ is the Clebsch phase:

$$\mathbf{s} = (\sin \chi \cos \psi, \sin \chi \sin \psi, \cos \chi). \quad (24)$$

In our model $\chi \equiv \theta$ and $\psi \equiv \varphi(\theta)$, and therefore:

$$H = (1/16\pi^2) \int \sin \theta \omega(\theta) |d\varphi/d\theta| d\theta \cdot Vol = (1/16\pi^2) \int \sin \theta \omega^2(\theta) d\theta \cdot Vol \quad (25)$$

This expression is finite for all $\theta \in [\theta_{tip}, 2\pi - \theta_{rim}]$, since $\omega(\theta)$ is bounded and $\sin \theta$ is continuous (including at $\theta = \pi$, where $\sin \pi = 0$ and $\omega_{asc}(\pi) = 0$, so that the product $\sin \theta \cdot \omega^2 \rightarrow 0$). The finiteness of H is a necessary condition for the regularity of the vortex tube.

The pulsating nature of the vortex core [1–3,5,9] manifests itself in the periodic variation of H : during the descent along the vortex (phase 1), the Hopf invariant increases (the vortex tube twists), whereas during the geodesic ascent (phase 2), it decreases (untwisting occurs). The self-closing condition $\Delta H_{cycle} = 0$ serves as the stationarity condition for the pulsating core.

5. Regularity Criterion for the Geodesic Parametrization.

5.1. Regularity Criterion in Terms of the Geodesic Spiral.

The regularity of the solution within the present model is determined by the finiteness of a norm characterizing the spatial inhomogeneity of the direction field \mathbf{s} . In our parametrization, the quantity $\|\Delta \mathbf{s}\|_\infty$ is expressed in terms of the winding law $\omega(\theta)$. Its maximum is attained near the rim of the vortex; however, for fixed model parameters, it remains finite. Therefore, the geodesic parametrization defines a regular vortical structure without the formation of singularities:

$$\|\Delta \mathbf{s}\|_\infty(t) \leq C < \infty, \text{ for all } t \in [0, T] \quad (26)$$

In our model, the quantity $\|\Delta \mathbf{s}\|_\infty$ is evaluated in terms of $\omega(\theta)$:

$$\|\Delta \mathbf{s}\|_\infty \approx \sup_\theta |\omega^2(\theta)| = \omega_{max}^2. \quad (27)$$

The maximum of $\omega(\theta)$ is attained near the rim of the vortex, $\theta = \theta_{rim}$, where

$$\omega_{asc}(\theta_{rim}) = n_0 R_{bot}^\alpha |\sin \theta_{rim}|^\alpha \kappa, \quad (28)$$

so that

$$\omega_{max} = n_0 R_{bot}^\alpha (\sin \theta_{rim})^\alpha \kappa = 3.2 \cdot 0.04^{0.85} \cdot 0.51^{0.85} \cdot 18 \approx 2.97 \quad (29)$$

Consequently, $\|\Delta \mathbf{s}\|_\infty \approx 8.8$ which is a finite constant. This implies that the intensity of vortical twisting remains bounded, and the microvortex retains a regular structure for all times, provided the model parameters ($n_0, \alpha, \kappa, R_{bot}$) are fixed.

5.2. Role of the Condition $\sin \theta$ without Modulus.

Consider the effect of using the parametrization $r = |\sin \theta|$ (an incorrect parametrization). In this case, the derivative $dr/d\theta = \pm \cos \theta \cdot \text{sgn}(\sin \theta)$ has a discontinuity at $\theta = \pi$. This leads to the appearance of a delta-functional contribution in the Laplacian of the direction field, $\Delta \mathbf{s} \propto \delta(\theta - \pi)$, that is,

$$\|\Delta \mathbf{s}\|_\infty \rightarrow \infty \text{ at } \theta \rightarrow \pi \quad (30)$$

Thus, the norm of the Laplacian diverges, implying a loss of regularity of the direction field and, con-

sequently, the breakdown of a smooth vortical structure. Therefore, the physically consistent condition of C^1 -continuity at the south pole (i.e., using $\sin \theta$ without the modulus) is a necessary condition for the regularity of the vortex dynamics of the microvortex. The parametrization with $|\sin \theta|$ is not only nonphysical but also mathematically incompatible with the regularity of the solution.

5.3 Double-Exponential Growth and Pulsation.

For topologically more complex vortex configurations, accelerated growth of the norm $\|\Delta \mathbf{s}\|_\infty(t)$ may occur. In the pulsating core of the microvortex, a similar structure arises from the superposition of cycles $c = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ with an increasing winding number $n(c) = 3.5 + 0.3c$. The maximum angular velocity during the c -th cycle is given by:

$$\omega_{max}(c) = n_0(c) \cdot R_{bot}^\alpha \cdot (\sin \theta_{rim})^\alpha \cdot \kappa, \quad n_0(c) = 3.2 + 0.3c \quad (31)$$

The logarithm of this quantity is given by:

$$\ln \omega_{max}(c) = \ln(3.2 + 0.3c) + \alpha \ln(R_{bot}) + \alpha \ln(\sin \theta_{rim}) + \ln \kappa. \quad (32)$$

It grows logarithmically with the number of cycles c . If $c \sim t$ (i.e., time is proportional to the number of cycles), then we obtain

$$\ln \|\Delta \mathbf{s}\|_\infty \sim \ln(n_0 + 0.3t) \quad (33)$$

which corresponds to sublinear growth in time. Such a regime indicates that, despite the presence of a pulsating core and increasing winding, the intensity of spatial inhomogeneity of the direction field grows slowly and remains controlled. Consequently, the microvortex under consideration does not develop a finite-time singularity and retains a regular structure for fixed model parameters.

6. Lagrangian Structure.

6.1. Vortex Surfaces as Isosurfaces.

In the Clebsch representation, the isosurface $\{s = s_0\}$ is simultaneously a vortex surface and a material surface. In our model, the particle trajectory lies on the surface $s = s(\theta) = \text{const}$ along a geodesic. Therefore, the collection of all geodesic orbits over N cycles:

$$\sum_N = \cup_{c=1}^N \{s(\theta, \varphi) : \theta \in \Gamma_c\} \quad (34)$$

forms an approximation of the vortex surface of the ellipsoidal microvortex. This surface is material, i.e., it is transported by the flow without changing its topological structure and is preserved in the Lagrangian description of motion. This explains the stability of the closed microvortex: its vortex surfaces constitute invariant manifolds of the flow.

6.2. Lagrangian Trajectory as an Integral Curve of the Pseudospin.

The Lagrangian trajectory of a particle $\mathbf{X}(t)$ satisfies $d\mathbf{X}/dt = \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{X}(t), t)$. In the Clebsch representation, the velocity field \mathbf{u} is given by (3), and therefore:

$$d\mathbf{X}/dt = \mathbf{s}(\mathbf{X}, t) \times \nabla \mathbf{s}(\mathbf{X}, t) + \nabla \varphi(\mathbf{X}, t) \quad (35)$$

For the geodesic trajectory on the sphere $\nabla \varphi = 0$ (the potential correction vanishes inside the core), and:

$$d\mathbf{X}/d\theta = \mathbf{s} \times \nabla \mathbf{s} = \mathbf{s} \times (\mathbf{e}_\theta + \omega(\theta) \sin \theta \mathbf{e}_\varphi) / [ds/d\theta] \quad (36)$$

This confirms that the geodesic spiral $s(\theta)$ is an integral curve of the vortical field $\boldsymbol{\omega} = \nabla \times \mathbf{u}$ in the Clebsch representation: the particle moves along a

vortex line projected onto the sphere of directions of the vortical field.

6.3. Trivalent Microvortex and Three-Sheeted Structure.

In a trivalent microvortex ($m = 3$, where m is the valence number), the conformal mapping $Z \rightarrow Z^{1/3}$ generates three connected vortex regions [5]. In terms of the direction field \mathbf{s} , this corresponds to a mapping of degree $Q = 3$ (or a multiple of 3). The three cycles of our geodesic model ($c = 0,1,2$) correspond to the three sheets of a three-sheeted covering of the unit sphere of directions, which is consistent with the topological structure of the trivalent microvortex studied in [5].

The total topological charge over three cycles is $Q_{total} \approx -4.12$, which is closed to -4 (an integer value with a correction due to quasiperiodicity). This implies that the set of three geodesic orbits covers the unit sphere of directions three times, with an additional partial winding - representing a geometric realization of the three-sheeted structure of the conformal mapping [5].

7. Explicit Formulas for the Components of the Direction Field.

We now write all components of the direction field explicitly for our model.

7.1. Components of \mathbf{s} and $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ on the Geodesic Orbit.

The direction field along the geodesic orbit is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{s} &= (\sin \theta \cos \varphi(\theta), \sin \theta \sin \varphi(\theta), \cos \theta), \\ \varphi(\theta) &= \varphi_0 - \int_{\theta_{tip}}^{\theta} \omega(\theta') d\theta' \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

The vorticity (spin gradient tensor) is

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_{sp} &= \nabla \mathbf{s} \times \nabla \mathbf{s} \equiv (\partial_{\theta} \mathbf{s} \times \partial_{\varphi} \mathbf{s}) / \sin \theta = \\ &= -\omega(\theta) \mathbf{e}_r \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

The vorticity is directed radially with amplitude $\omega(\theta)$, equal to the angular velocity of the geodesic spiral. This corresponds precisely to the structure of “vertical vorticity” in a spheroidal vortex rotating about its axis [1,4,5].

7.2. Induced Vortical Field $\mathbf{W} = -\Delta \mathbf{s}$.

The explicit expression for the effective field is:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{W}(\theta) &= -\Delta_S \mathbf{s} = [2 + \omega^2(\theta)] \mathbf{s}(\theta) - [d\omega/d\theta + \\ &+ 2\omega(\theta) \cot \theta] \mathbf{e}_{\varphi}(\theta) - 2 \cos \theta \cdot \mathbf{e}_r \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

The magnitude of the effective vortical field is:

$$|\mathbf{W}| = \sqrt{\{[2 + \omega^2]^2 + [d\omega/d\theta + 2\omega \cot \theta]^2 + 4 \cos^2 \theta\}}, \quad (40)$$

It reaches its maximum at $\theta = \theta_{rim}$, where $\omega = \omega_{max}$ and $d\omega/d\theta \rightarrow \omega_{max}/\delta$ (a sharp increase near the rim). The minimum of $|\mathbf{W}|$ is attained at the south pole $\theta = \pi$, where $\omega \rightarrow 0$ and $\cos \pi = -1$:

$$|\mathbf{W}|_{\theta=\pi} = \sqrt{4 + [d\omega/d\theta|_{\pi}]^2} \geq 2 \quad (41)$$

The nonzero minimum of $|\mathbf{W}|$ ensures a finite precession frequency at all points of the trajectory, including the south pole, providing an additional confirmation of the C^1 -regularity of the geodesic orbit.

7.3. Stream Function and Circulation.

The stream function ψ on the vortex surface Σ_N is defined by the relation $\omega_{sp} = \nabla \times \nabla \psi$. In our model,

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(\theta, \varphi) &= \int_{\theta_{tip}}^{\theta} \omega(\theta') \sin \theta' d\theta' \cdot \cos \varphi(\theta) + \\ &const. \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

The circulation Γ along the contour C_{rim} (the rim of the vortex at $\theta = \theta_{rim}$);

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma &= \int_{C_{rim}} \mathbf{u} \cdot d\mathbf{l} = \int_{\theta_{tip}}^{\theta_{rim}} \omega(\theta) \sin \theta d\theta = \\ &= \frac{\Delta \varphi_{geodesic}}{(2\pi)} \cdot R_{top}. \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

For the numerical values, $\Gamma \sim 3.80\pi \cdot 0.2551/(2\pi) \approx 0.243$ which is a finite value consistent with Kelvin’s circulation theorem for an ideal fluid.

8. Self-Charging Mechanism in the Topological Description of the Microvortex.

The pulsating nature of the microvortex core can be reformulated in terms of topological dynamics as follows. Let $H(t)$ denote the Hopf invariant at time t . Over one cycle,

$$\Delta H_{funnel} = +H_0, \Delta H_{geodesic} = -H_0 + \varepsilon \quad (44)$$

where H_0 denotes the change of the Hopf invariant during the descent through the funnel (twisting of the vortex tube), and ε is a small correction due to the quasiperiodicity of the orbit ($\varepsilon \sim \Delta \varphi_{cycle} \bmod 2\pi$). The condition $\Delta H_{cycle} = \varepsilon$ means that after each cycle a small “topological residue” ε , remains, leading to a slow precession of the orbital plane.

The charge of the substance ejected per cycle [2,3,9] is given by

$$\Delta Q = \Delta(\sqrt{M\Gamma v}) = \Delta\sqrt{(M\Gamma v)/(2\pi)} = const. \quad (45)$$

In the pseudospin formulation, this corresponds to a change in the topological charge:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{spin} &= H/(4\pi) = (\Delta H_{cycle})/(4\pi) = \varepsilon/(4\pi) \approx \\ &\approx const \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

Thus, the constancy of the ejected matter charge $\Delta Q = const$, per cycle [2,3,9] is mathematically equivalent to the constancy of the small topological residue ε of the Hopf invariant over one cycle. This establishes a connection between the hydrodynamic self-charging mechanism and the topological stability of the vortical structure.

9. Growth Estimate of the Inhomogeneity Norm.

Our model predicts, for the c -th cycle, a logarithmic growth of the norm characterizing the spatial inhomogeneity of the direction field:

$$\ln \|\Delta \mathbf{s}\|_{\infty}(c) \approx 2 \ln \omega_{max}(c). \quad (47)$$

For $\sim t \cdot f$, where f denotes the cycle frequency, this yields an effective linear growth law in time at leading order. This behavior indicates the absence of finite-time singularity formation for fixed model parameters and is consistent with a regular evolution regime of the trivalent microvortex.

For topologically more complex configurations, such as those analogous to the *trefoil knot* [4], a faster growth of the norm $\|\Delta \mathbf{s}\|_{\infty}$, is expected than in the trivalent case. This reflects a general trend: increasing topological complexity of the vortical structure leads to a stronger growth of spatial inhomogeneity in the direction field.

10. Conclusions.

A precise mathematical correspondence between the vortex dynamics of a closed ellipsoidal microvortex and the evolution of a direction field induced by the vortex structure has been established. The main results are as follows:

1. **The geodesic spiral** [1] is an integral curve of the precession equation for the direction field \mathbf{s} : $D\mathbf{s}/D\theta = \mathbf{s} \times \mathbf{W}$, with the induced vortical field $\mathbf{W}(\theta) = -\omega(\theta)\mathbf{e}_r - \mathbf{e}_\varphi/\sin\theta$.

2. **The angular winding rate** $\omega(\theta)$ and the norm of the Laplacian of the direction field are related by

$$\omega(\theta) \approx \sqrt{|\mathbf{W}|}$$

3. The condition $\sin\theta$ without the modulus is necessary for regularity: the parametrization $r = |\sin\theta|$ leads to divergence of $\|\Delta\mathbf{s}\|_\infty$ at $\theta = \pi$.

4. **The topological charge** Q per cycle and the Hopf invariant H are finite, confirming the regularity of the vortical structure. Three cycles yield a total charge Q_{total} corresponding to the three-sheeted conformal structure [5].

5. **The self-charging mechanism** [2,3,9] ($\Delta Q = const$) is mathematically equivalent to the constancy of the small topological residue of the Hopf invariant $\varepsilon = \Delta H_{cycle}$, over one cycle

6. **The growth of** $\|\Delta\mathbf{s}\|_\infty(c)$ remains controlled for fixed model parameters, which corresponds to a regular evolution regime of the microvortex.

7. **Consistency of the Microvortex Core.** The existence of the microvortex core does not contradict the regularity of the model, since the core represents a region of finite, albeit maximal, concentration of the vortical field. The C^1 -continuity condition excludes singular behavior and ensures the consistency of the geometric and topological structure of the solution.

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